

Tool: The Future Mobility Newspaper

Description	Future Journals represent one way to engage citizens in the production of dissemination material to reach both public authorities and the civic society as a whole. The tool consists of a canvas to facilitate the capturing of inputs when envisioning future scenarios. The canvas gives a structured way to envision and effectively communicate future desirable scenarios. It includes: a headline and additional elements to describe the journey to the establishment of such scenarios (e.g. the enabling policies and other resources, a list and timeline of actions, stakeholders to be involved etc).
Why am I doing it?	Envisioning future scenarios to address concerns emerging from the pilot's findings. Stimulate creativity of participants in designing new action - oriented solutions.
Which kind of issue can I tackle?	Potentially applicable to all citizen science projects
Resources needed	Printed Future Journal Canvas, markers and post-its; public space; one facilitator per group / table.
Time needed	1 to 2 hours
Skills needed	Subject-matter expertise: Basic IT skills: Not Required Facilitation skills: Intermediate Event organisation skills: Intermediate Project management skills: Basic Communication skills: Intermediate
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The team convenes in a public space. 2. Citizens and other participants are divided into groups of 4-7 people. 3. A facilitator guides the emergence of creative ideas about desirable future scenarios around sustainable mobility. 4. Collectively agree on a story title and populate the canvas. This is done through outlining the journey to be undertaken to make the future scenarios real. 5. Disseminate the Future Journal through appropriate means.
Outcomes	Dissemination material targeting both the overall civic society and public authorities.
Tips!	Stimulate the group to be visionary and force them to envision the optimal situation in 5 years from now!